

Consumers' Omnichannel Integration Quality, Credibility and Innovativeness Perceptions of the Brands and Omnichannel Adoptions

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Abstract

In this study it is aimed to reveal how brands' omnichannel integration quality, omnichannel credibility and perceived innovativeness influence consumers' omnichannel adoption and to reveal the mediating role of perceived omnichannel value on this effect. Also, it examines the omnichannel usage in tourism, banking, clothing and furniture sectors. For this purpose, the data obtained by sending an online questionnaire via social media applications and via email to 411 people from different cities and having different demographic characteristics were analyzed by SEM method. According to the results of the analysis, a relationship was found between omnichannel integration quality, omnichannel credibility and perceived brand innovativeness. In addition, it was concluded that perceived omnichannel value has a mediating role in the effect of omnichannel credibility and brand innovativeness variables on the omnichannel adoption variable, while it does not have a mediating role in the effect of the omnichannel integration quality variable on the omnichannel adoption variable. It is thought that this study and the results obtained are important in terms of being a guide in theory and practice, since the variables in the study are related to the use of omnichannel in the product and service purchasing processes of consumers.

Key words: Omnichannel integration quality, omnichannel credibility, brand innovativeness, perceived omnichannel value, omnichannel adoption

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1. Introduction

The most important striking power of our age is applications based on innovations that challenge even our imagination day by day in terms of technology. Thanks to the information processing technologies that open new doors to the business world, businesses are now almost competing to restructure their functions in accordance with the requirements of the age and in this way to gain the advantage that will create competitive value. This race also increases the efforts to keep up with the technological change and development among many brands and products that replace each other. Undoubtedly, efforts to offer new and unique value to consumers have opened the door to important new applications brought by the world of technology to businesses that want to be in a closer and integrated communication platform with their consumers.

It is very important that distribution, which is one of the elements of the marketing mix in its essence, is carried out more systematically throughout the distribution channel and in an integrated manner among all channel members. The omnichannel strategy, in which all distribution and communication channels are integrated and uninterrupted in order for many retailers to remain competitive, continues to attract the attention of customers in different fields (Lee et al, 2019). The omnichannel strategy fully integrates all consumer touchpoints and data sources to deliver unseen experiences to consumers regardless of how and where they choose to interact with the brand (desktop or mobile device, phone, or physical store, etc.) (Chaffey, Hemphill and Edmundson - Bird, 2019).

This strategy, where businesses can offer the consumer a purchasing experience using enriching integrated channels, with an increasing number of consumer touchpoints and empowers the consumer to have more control over the purchasing journey. The practices of businesses based on creating and offering the most value and shopping options to their customers continue to increase with the rapid innovations of the digital world. In this study, the "omnichannel strategy", which can be explained as an innovation that integrates digital with traditional, has been investigated in terms of delivering tourism products and services to consumers. In addition, the mediating role of tourism brands' omnichannel integration quality, omnichannel credibilities and innovativeness perceptions on the effect of consumers' perceived value on omnichannel adaptation has been examined. Since the important thing is the success of capturing and applying the value that these innovations add to fields such as business and marketing and to consumers in practice, it is thought that this research will be a guide.

2. Literature Review

Omnichannel Concept

Numerous terms are used in the literature to describe the concepts of strategy based on several channels, and these terms include "channel integration",

"cross-channel", "multi-channel", "multi-channel" and other variations (Hajdas, Radomska and Silva, 2022). Verhoef, Kannan and Inman (2015) defined omnichannel strategy as "synergistic management of multiple existing channels and customer touchpoints so that customer experience across channels and performance across channels are optimized".

When asked to define multi-channel distribution, we went with single-channel multi-channel, and in the 21st century, the phrase was cross-channel. We started to see greater integration between brick-and-mortar and online channels, and more functionality between the two. But it was episodic. Omnichannel is the latest stage of evolution, from a single channel to a complete and comprehensive experience that connects these different touch points (Harris 2012).

The evolution of technology and digitalization efforts strongly influences how consumers behave, how markets evolve, and how businesses and consumers interact. The omnichannel strategy is a concept that allows consumers to use channels seamlessly and interchangeably and to experience channels in a unique way (Mirsch, Lehrer and Jung, 2016). In other words, omnichannel is defined as a strategy focused on the integration and coordination of separate channels to meet the needs of consumers with seamless channel transitions.

Figure 1. Omnichannel (Source: Haan, 2019)

Receiving integrated channel (omnichannel) service means being able to communicate with the brand through all channels such as "phone, internet, mobile application, physical store" during the product or service purchasing process (information-research, decision-making, purchasing, commenting afterwards, etc.) and purchasing products/services.

Brand omnichannel integration quality

Channel integration quality is defined as the ability to provide customers with a seamless and unified service experience across different channels (Shen, Li, Sun and Wang, 2018). Channel integration quality includes breadth, transparency, content consistency and process consistency. Breadth is the degree to which various channels can support the same tasks. Transparency means that the client is aware of the existence and capabilities of each channel. Content consistency is that each channel transmits the same information. Content consistency also refers to the channel's ability to undo the customer's previous actions or actions. Process consistency is whether the channels are consistent in features related to the shopping process, that is, the look, feel and service quality for the store, call center and website should be the same (Neslin, 2022).

Brand omnichannel credibility

For the 21st century, credibility is to integrate the perspectives on message, source and media reliability in contemporary media (as cited in, Oyedeji, 2007). In the field of branding, trust is a psychological variable observation that reflects a set of assumptions that include a brand's reliability, honesty, and goodwill (Gurviez et al., 2003). When a consumer trusts the brand, he or she becomes more loyal to the brand, is persuaded to pay more, buys new products in existing or new categories, and tells his or her choices and preferences and also it has been observed that brand trust has a direct effect on brand value (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2001). Subsequent studies have focused on the effects of source, medium, audience and message characteristics on credibility (Metzger et al., 2003)

Brand innovativeness

According to Rogers (2003:12), innovation is ideas, practices, or objects that individuals or businesses perceive as new. Organizational innovation means that businesses have an open stance to innovation, are sensitive to innovations in their environment and can adapt to these innovations (Aksoy and Yıldız, 2015: 190). It is possible to say that businesses are making more efforts in branding day by day. Perceiving innovation as specific to the brand can be defined as brand innovativeness. According to Eisingerich and Rubera (2010: 66), brand innovativeness is defined as the perception of brands by consumers as having the ability to find solutions to meet the needs of consumers.

Perceived omnichannel value

Consumers' perceived trust and satisfaction about their holistic channel shopping experience and purchase intention are important (Zhang et al., 2018). The holistic channel experience takes place during a retailer's customer interaction through different channels and offers value for the customer. In other words, retailers can take advantage of the convenience of using all channels together or in an integrated way and to serve customers with different needs (Verhoef et al., 2015). The holistic channel strategy focuses on the customer and aims to provide him with a seamless experience (Juaneda-Ayensa, Mosquera, & Murillo, 2016).

Omnichannel adoption

An integrated channel strategy is the retailer's effort to reach the consumer through all possible channels. These channels include physical stores, catalogues, telephone, online shopping and mobile shopping. In addition to interacting in these channels, the consumer or retailer can seek full coordination between these channels, in other words adoption. When the integrated channel strategy works from the consumer's point of view, the consumer can return a product purchased online to the nearest physical store to the workplace. At this point, it doesn't matter where you bought the product or where you will return it. When the integrated channel strategy works from the retailer's point of view, it provides the transfer of the information about the customer, price and inventory to all channels and thus a full adaptation between the channels from the retailer point of view (Beck and Rygl, 2015).

The relationships between brand omnichannel integration quality, brand omnichannel credibility, brand innovativeness

According to Sousa & Voss (2006), service quality in an integrated channel retail environment basically consists of online, physical and integration quality components. As retail businesses increasingly use physical and online channels for customer communication, providing a seamless customer experience within and between channels has highlighted the integration quality of integrated channel services becoming more important. Gao & Huang (2021) stated that psychological and behavioral customer loyalty plays a vital role in Omnichannel communication; found that an uninterrupted, consistent, and reassuring environment leads to customer engagement and loyalty. For this reason, the reliability of Omnichannel is important. Hossain et al. (2019), integration quality also offers assurance channel quality. Assurance quality refers to reliability. It has been stated that multiple channel features, including privacy and security, can recover customers' personal information in channels as well as accessibility services. Quach et al. (2022) suggested that retailers adopting the omnichannel strategy can reduce the perceived risk of customers and thus increase reliability, as the integration of transaction information with service and product information consistency, which can increase

customer satisfaction. In the light of this information, the following hypothesis was formed:

H₁: There is a relationship between brand omnichannel integration quality and brand omnichannel credibility

Innovative businesses may face marketing challenges such as adapting to new technologies, new processes, new distribution channels, new competitors or new customers (Shams, Alpert and Brown, 2015). Brand innovativeness refers to the degree to which consumers perceive a brand as innovative (Barone & Jewell, 2013; Barone & Jewell, 2014). Henard & Dacin (2010) stated that brand innovation positively affects perceived quality and customer loyalty. According to Martínez-de Albéniz & Belkaid (2020), innovative approaches and the implementation of omnichannel strategies are important for operational processes in the retail sector. According to Mukherjee & Hoyer (2001), brand innovation increases brand loyalty in the channel and reflects the innovative firm mentality. According to Jin et al. (2015) states that perception image of restaurant innovativeness affects brand credibility and brand preference, also brand credibility affects customer loyalty and brand preference. So;

H₂: There is a relationship between brand omnichannel credibility and brand innovativeness

According to Juaneda-Ayensa et al. (2016), omnichannel strategies focus on the customer and aim to provide him with a seamless experience. Beck & Rygl, (2015) and Rippe et al., (2015) states that omnichannel strategies are presented in a holistic way as if all distribution points are part of a single design, and with this strategy, customers are not tied to only one channel, so they can reach the product more easily, eliminate the pressure of the salesperson, They can take control, benefit from discounts in the same way in all channels, and stated that there is consistency in product and service diversity, innovation and prices across all channels. Pappu & Quester (2016) found that brand innovativeness has a positive effect on the perceived quality of the product.

H₃: There is a relationship between brand omnichannel integration quality and brand innovativeness.

Omnichannel activities need to be optimized to streamline processes, coordinate channels, customer interactions, touch points, and create a synergy. In this context, it is seen that this synergy can be more effective with Omnichannel Integration Quality, Omnichannel Credibility and Brand Innovativeness.

The relationships between brand omnichannel integration quality, brand omnichannel credibility, brand innovativeness and perceived omnichannel value, omnichannel adoption

Wu & Chang (2016) found that channel integration quality increases customers' perceived value when shopping online. According to Hamouda (2019), channel integration quality plays an important role, positively affecting satisfaction and perceived value. According to Krafft et al. (2015), channel integration is also the most important element of marketing in creating value chain. Hure, Picot-Coupey and Ackerman (2017) argued that the integration of the omnichannel strategy enables different channels and touchpoints to cooperate, and this cooperation creates value for the customer by targeting an optimal customer experience. Shen et al. (2018) found that the quality of Omnichannel channel integration has a significant impact on customer behavior. Channel integration quality facilitates the consumer's perceived fluency in their shopping, and thus the perceived channel value of the omnichannel emerges. Based on the literature and in the light of these studies, the H4 hypothesis has been developed.

H 4: Brand omnichannel integration quality affects perceived omnichannel value

Morgan and Hunt (1994), in the retail industry, consumers may view a retailer as more reliable when they perceive it as more valuable than others. Verhagen, Meents and Tan (2006) stated that consumers who trust the business are highly likely to prefer shopping from omnichannels. Li et al. (2018) founded that omnichannel has positive effects on customer retention. Chen & Chi (2021) stated that products and prices that are well integrated across sales channels successfully reduce the risk perceived by consumers. In this context, it can be stated that omnichannel reliability will increase the perceived channel value. Gao and Yang (2016) stated that the omnichannel strategy can provide customers with seamless experiences by securely allowing them to create actions across channels without any difference in the areas of product and pricing, promotion, transaction information, information access, and offer channel value with order fulfillment and customer service. Chaudhuri and Holbrook (2001) concluded in their study that brand trust has a direct effect on brand equity.

H 5: Brand omnichannel credibility affects perceived omnichannel value

Steenkamp, Hofstede and Wedel (1999) state that consumers' attitudes differ according to new and innovative products. Pappu and Quester (2016) states that perceived quality, brand innovativeness has an impact on brand loyalty. In other words, consumer perceptions of brand innovativeness affect brand loyalty, which is an important brand performance measure. According to Neslin (2022), while expanding the channel selection, the omnichannel strategy also affects customer-brand-retail channel interactions. Schlager & Maas (2013) explain that

omnichannel strategy is changing the increasing adoption of new innovations in retail, changing customer expectations and value.

H 6: Brand innovativeness affects perceived omnichannel value

Climent (2022) provides a good market fit if a new omnichannel configuration, that is, channels included and the way they are integrated, is in some sense new and has a new business model. The Omnichannel strategy is then more likely to attract new customers to the channel. Melero et al., (2016) states that in omnichannel, consumers can move freely between all channels in a single transaction, this ensures channel adaptation. Eggert and Ulaga (2001) states that perceived value plays a decisive role in estimating consumer behavior, ensuring sustainable competitive advantage, and decisions on developing new product and service strategy. Also, eWOM credibility is always a major concern for eWOM receivers and review credibility, in turn, is found to have a significant impact on subsequent adoption (Cheung, Luo, Sia & Chen, 2009).

H 7: Perceived omnichannel value affects omnichannel adoption

The structure and the mediator role of perceived omnichannel value

Mirzabeiki and Saghiri (2020) found that achieving holistic channel integration is key enablers for data capture and data sharing for omnichannel data integration, and the expansion of omnichannel data management to customers, manufacturers and logistics services enables omnichannel data integration. According to King et al. (2004) channel integration ensures that consumers have a seamless shopping experience. Gasparin (2020) shows that perceived channel integration has a positive effect on customer experience, which in turn affects customer trust and loyalty. Lopes (2020) found that omnichannel awareness and quality of channel integration are associated with customer engagement and its outcomes. He stated that the consistent integration of the omnichannel makes customers feel more empowered and encourages them to repurchase brands' products and share positive reviews about the brand with other individuals. Hickman et al., (2020) explains the factors affecting the omnichannel experience. He emphasized that many factors such as brand awareness, customization, perceived value and technology should be taken into account.

Figure 2: Information Adoption Model
(Source: Sussman & Siegal, 2003)

The model of this study is based on Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989), Planned Behavior Theory (Ajzen, 1991), Information Adoption Model (Figure 2, Sussman & Siegal, 2003), Wixom and Todd Model (Figure 3, Wixom and Todd, 2005). According to Wixom and Todd model, reliability affect system quality. In our study, we examine the relationship between Omnichannel Credibility (related reliability) and Omnichannel Integration Quality (as system quality) as components of Object Based Beliefs. There are studies which state that customer's credibility perceptions affect their behavioral intentions (Nechoud, Ghidouche & Seraphin, 2021; Anubha & Shome, 2020). Also we added Brand innovativeness as a component of object based beliefs. Because, studies show that there is a relationship between innovativeness and quality (Pappu & Quester, 2016); between innovativeness and perceived value (Schlager & Maas, 2013); between innovativeness and credibility (Shams, Brown & Alpert, 2017; Jin et al. 2015).

Studies show that information credibility is an important element for adoption (Fang, 2014; Lis, 2013, Tien & Amaya, 2018). The analyses indicate that there is a significant relationship between customer satisfaction and perceived value, and that perceived value is an important priority for customer satisfaction and to ensure and maintain customer satisfaction. Also, it is necessary to organize the service provided in a way that affects the perceived value of the consumer (Eskiler & Altunışık, 2015). At this point, it may be important to investigate whether perceived value has a mediating role in the effects of omnichannel credibility, omnichannel integration quality and brand innovativeness on consumers' omnichannel adaptations.

H₈: Perceived omnichannel value mediates the relationship between brand omnichannel integration quality and omnichannel adoption

H₉: Perceived omnichannel value mediates the relationship between brand omnichannel credibility and omnichannel adoption

H₁₀: Perceived omnichannel value mediates the relationship between brand innovativeness and omnichannel adoption

Figure 3: Wixom and Todd's Model (Source: Wixom and Todd, 2005)

Wixom and Todd states that object-based beliefs form object-based attitudes information and satisfaction with the system, which in turn influences behavioral beliefs such as perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use and thus behavioral attitude and intention (Wixom and Todd, 2005)

In the light of all these studies, the model of the research is formed as follows:

Reliability ➡ Omnichannel ➡ Credibility
 System information service Quality ➡ Omnichannel Integration Quality
 Satisfaction, usefulness, ease of use, enjoyment ➡
 Perceived Omnichannel Value
 Attitude, intention ➡ Omnichannel Adoption

Thus, the model of the study is formed as given in Figure 4.

Object – Based Beliefs

Figure 4. Research Model

Object Based Beliefs

Brand-Omnichannel Integration Quality
 Brand-Omnichannel Credibility
 Brand Innovativeness

Attitudes and Beliefs

Perceived Omnichannel Value

Behavioral Attitudes

Omnichannel Adoption

3. Methodology

Participants

The universe of the research consists of consumers using integrated channel applications. “Easy sampling method” was used in the research. In the research, "survey technique" was used as a data collection tool. The questionnaires were directed to as many people as possible online. All adults who were able to use the integrated channel applications were included in the study. The surveys were applied between September 2022 and February 2023. It was sent to 500 people and valid responses were received from 411 people. It was determined that the number of participants should be more than 200 participants to apply confirmatory factor analysis and SEM to the analysis (Hair et al., 2010). The data obtained were evaluated with a statistical analysis program. The data were subjected to factor

analysis, reliability analysis, correlation analysis and regression analysis. Table 1 shows descriptive statistics.

The participants were first asked whether they used the "omnichannel" such as telephone, internet, mobile application, physical store in the process of purchasing products or services (information-research, decision-making, purchasing, and then commenting, etc.). Questionnaires of the participants which stated that they did not use omnichannel were not included in the study. Then, it was asked which sectors they use all channels of a brand (phone, internet, mobile application, physical store). According to the literature it is possible to say that omnichannel applications are not evenly distributed and in general, omnichannel strategies applied in the tourism, finance and fashion sectors yield better results (Mosquera, Olarte Pascual and Juaneda Ayensa, 2017; Verhoef et al., 2015; Mainardes, de Moura Rosa and Nossa, 2019; Lynch and Barnes, 2020; Oktay, 2021). Also taking into account the brands that use omnichannel in Turkey, options such as "clothing (clothing, shoes, etc.)", "banking", "furniture", "food and beverage", "tourism" and "other sectors" were added to the questionnaire. Distribution of the participants in the study according to their socio-demographic characteristics is given in Table 1.

Table 1: The Results of the Descriptive Statistics

Variables	n	%	
Gender	woman	225	54.7
	male	186	45.3
age ($\bar{X} \pm SD$, 29.20 \pm 8.82)	20 years and under	72	17.5
	21-30	177	43.1
	31-40	113	27.5
	41 years and older	49	11.9
educational status	primary school	18	4.4
	middle school	21	5.1
	high school	125	30.4
	associate degree	53	12.9
	license	176	42.8
	graduate	18	4.4
marital status	married	205	49.9
	single	206	50.1

job		public employee	20	4.9
		private sector	27	6.6
		teacher	18	4.4
		engineer	11	2.7
		employee	10	2.4
		student	108	26.3
		housewife	88	21.4
		not working	18	4.4
		other	111	27.0
omnichannel usage	clothing	yes	351	85.4
		no	60	14.6
	banking	yes	261	63.5
		no	150	36.5
	furniture	yes	93	22.6
		no	318	77.4
	tourism-food and beverage	yes	262	63.7
		no	149	36.3
	tourism-hotel,ticket,tour..etc.	yes	87	21.2
		no	324	78.8
	other	yes	35	8.5
		no	376	91.5
total		411	100.0	

Measures

Scales in the study consist of five parts. These sections are omnichannel integration quality, omnichannel credibility, brand innovation, omnichannel value, and omnichannel adoption sections.

The Perceived Omnichannel Integration Quality Scale consists of five statements and is adapted for brands from Hamouda (2019)'s studies on the omnichannel integration quality of banks. When the reliability of the perceived integrated channel quality scale was evaluated, it was found to be 0.852 for the overall scale and it was found to have good reliability.

The Perceived Integrated Channel Confidence Scale consists of five items and was adapted for brands from the Meyer Credibility Scale included in West's (1994) study on credibility. When the reliability of the perceived integrated channel reliability scale was evaluated, it was found to be 0.874 for the overall scale and it was found to have good reliability.

The Perceived Brand Innovation Scale, which consists of eight statements, was adapted for brands from the scales of Duygun & Yücel (2018) regarding the perceived innovativeness of airline brands. When the reliability of the perceived brand innovativeness scale was evaluated, it was found to be 0.922 for the overall scale and it was found to have good reliability.

The Perceived Omnichannel Value Scale, consisting of five statements, was adapted from the study of Hamouda (2019) for brands. When the reliability of the perceived omnichannel value scale was evaluated, it was found to be 0.873 for the overall scale and it was found to have a good degree of reliability.

Omnichannel Adoption Scale is adapted for brands from the scale in Cheung et al.'s (2009) study on eWOM. When the reliability of the omnichannel adaptation scale was evaluated, it was found to be 0.880 for the overall scale and it was found to have a good degree of reliability.

Some of the scale questions were prepared in English and translated into Turkish by a bilingual academic to ensure validity. Items were rated on a 5-point Likert-type scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Data Analysis

PSS 25.0 and AMOS 23.0 programs were used to perform SEM analysis. Initially, confirmatory factor analysis (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988) was used to assess the reliability and validity of the measures. SEM "is the preferred method of analysis when multiple relationships between different unobserved latent constructs must be simultaneously examined with considerable statistical precision" (Hair et al., 2010). First, a confirmatory factor analysis was performed in order to analyze the reliability and validity of all used scales (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988). A frequency analysis was then performed to determine the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants. The effects of omnichannel integration quality, omnichannel credibility and brand innovativeness on omnichannel perceived value and omnichannel adoption were examined with a structural equation model. Next, the mediating role of perceived omnichannel perceived value was analyzed.

4. Findings

Measurement model

"Reliability Analysis" was used to test the reliability of the scales, and "Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)" was used to test construct validity using the

Amos program. Path analyzes and mediation role were analyzed in line with the established model.

In SEM, the data set must provide a multivariate normal distribution (Byrne, 2001). In this context, multivariate extreme values were examined with Mahalanobis distance values. The Mahalanobis criterion based on the relationship between observations is recommended for the detection of outliers in multivariate and high-volume data sets with near-zero or negative-valued observations (Johnson and Wichern, 2002).

As outliers increase the value of error variance, they also affect the power of statistical tests. For this reason, outliers were examined before statistical tests, and it was checked whether they were present in the data sets. The presence of outlier-outliers was determined by the Mahalanobis method, and these values were removed from the data set to provide multiple normality criteria.

The conformity of the data used to the normal distribution was tested. Compliance with the normal distribution can be examined with the QQ Plot (Chan, 2003: 280-285). In addition, the normal distribution of the data used depends on the Skewness and Kurtosis values being between ± 3 (Shao, 2002).

In the comparison of quantitative data in normally distributed data, the independent t test was used for the difference between two independent groups, and one-way analysis of variance was applied in the comparison of more than 2 independent groups, and Bonferroni was used to find the group that made a difference when there was a difference. Pearson to test the relationship between numerical variables correlation was applied.

Correlation analysis results are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Correlation Analysis

	what's that	2	3	4	5
1- Detected Integrated Channel Quality	1,000	0.774	0.751	0.684	0.666
p	-	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*
2- Perceived Embedded Channel Confidence		1,000	0.780	0.664	0.697
p		-	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*
3- Perceived Omnichannel Value			1,000	0.803	0.764
p			-	0.000*	0.000*
4- Omnichannel Adoption				1,000	0.732
p				-	0.000*
5- Perceived Brand Innovation					1,000
p					-

Correlation analysis was applied to test the relationship between the scales used in the study. As a result, there were differences between perceived integrated channel quality and perceived integrated channel reliability ($r=0.774$, $p<0.05$),

perceived omnichannel value ($r=0.751$, $p<0.05$), omnichannel Adoption ($r=0.684$, $p<0.05$)) and It is seen that there is a statistically significant and positive relationship between perceived brand innovativeness ($r=0.666$, $p<0.05$).

There was a statistically and positive difference between perceived integrated channel reliability and perceived omnichannel value ($r=0.780$, $p<0.05$), between omnichannel adoption ($r=0.664$, $p<0.05$) and perceived brand innovativeness ($r=0.697$, $p<0.05$) 0.05). There appears to be a one-way relationship.

It is seen that there is a statistically significant and positive relationship between perceived omnichannel value and omnichannel adoption ($r=0.803$, $p<0.05$) and perceived brand innovativeness ($r=0.764$, $p<0.05$). It is seen that there is a statistically significant and positive relationship between omnichannel adoption and perceived brand innovativeness ($r=0.732$, $p<0.05$).

Structural Model

The structural model of the research based on the hypotheses is given in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Structural Model

Before examining the mediating role in the created model, it was examined whether the independent variable influenced the dependent variable. On omnichannel adoption of perceived integrated channel quality it was found to have a statistically significant effect ($\beta=0.782$, $p<0.05$). While the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable was significant, it was examined

whether there was a mediator role in this effect. The fact that the values in the 95% confidence interval include 0 according to the results of the model shows that there is no mediator role in the model (-0.023, 0.543).

Table 3: Results Regarding the Research Model

Effect	Guess	standard error	t	p	Conclusion	
H4: Perceived Integrated Channel Quality → Perceived Omnichannel Value	0.228	0.098	2.227	***	Acceptance	
H5: Perceived Embedded Channel Credibility → Perceived Omnichannel Value	0.398	0.113	3,655	***	Acceptance	
H6: Perceived Brand Innovativeness → Perceived Omnichannel Value	0.373	0.054	6,733	***	Acceptance	
H7: Perceived Omnichannel Value → Omnichannel Adoption	0.983	0.174	5,859	***	Acceptance	
H8: Perceived Integrated Channel Quality → Perceived Omnichannel Adoption	Effect	0.782	0.063	11,948	***	Acceptance
	Direct Impact	0.228	0.126	1,799	0.072	not accept
	Indirect Effect	0.224	Confidence Interval (-0.023, 0.543)			Not Significant
H9: Perceived Embedded Channel Credibility → Perceived Omnichannel Adoption	Effect	0.744	0.073	10,880	***	Acceptance
	Direct Impact	-0.458	0.166	-2.971	***	Acceptance
	Indirect Effect	0.391	Confidence Interval (0.094, 0.820)			Significant
H10: Perceived Brand Innovation → Perceived Omnichannel Adoption	Effect	0.809	0.060	13,471	***	Acceptance
	Direct Impact	0.155	0.085	1,834	0.067	not accept
	Indirect Effect	0.367	Confidence Interval (0.189, 0.638)			Significant

Compliance Values: χ^2/df : 2.446, RMSEA: 0.059, GFI: 0.880, AGFI: 0.856, CFI: 0.940, NFI: 0.904, IFI: 0.941, TLI: 0.933, SRMR: 0.034

On omnichannel adoption of perceived integrated channel reliability it was found to have a statistically significant effect ($\beta=0.744$, $p<0.05$). While the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable was significant, it was examined whether there was a mediator role in this effect. The fact that the values in the 95% confidence interval do not include 0 according to the results of the model shows that it has a mediator role in the model (0.094, 0.820). After deciding that there is an intermediary role, it was examined whether the direct effect was significant to decide on the type of this mediator role. As a result, it was seen that the direct effect was significant, but the effect coefficient decreased ($\beta= - 0.458$, $p<0.05$) and it was decided that the mediator was a partial mediator.

On the omnichannel adoption of perceived brand innovativeness it was found to have a statistically significant effect ($\beta=0.809$, $p<0.05$). While the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable was significant, it was examined whether there was a mediator role in this effect. The fact that the values

in the 95% confidence interval do not include 0 according to the results of the model shows that it has a mediating role in the model (0.189, 0.638). After deciding that there is an intermediary role, it was examined whether the direct effect was significant to decide on the type of this mediator role. As a result, it was seen that the direct effect was not significant ($\beta = -0.155, p > 0.05$) and it was decided that the mediator was the full mediator.

H₁: There is a relationship between brand omnichannel integration quality and brand omnichannel credibility (accepted)

H₂: There is a relationship between brand omnichannel credibility and brand innovativeness (accepted)

H₃: There is a relationship between brand omnichannel integration quality and brand innovativeness (accepted)

H₄: Brand omnichannel integration quality affect perceived omnichannel value (accepted)

H₅: Brand omnichannel credibility affect perceived omnichannel value (accepted)

H₆: Brand innovativeness affect perceived omnichannel value (accepted)

H₇: Perceived omnichannel value affect omnichannel adoption (accepted)

H₈: Perceived omnichannel value mediates the relationship between brand omnichannel integration quality and omnichannel adoption (not accepted)

H₉: Perceived omnichannel value mediates the relationship between brand omnichannel credibility and omnichannel adoption (accepted)

H₁₀: Perceived omnichannel value mediates the relationship between brand innovativeness and omnichannel adoption (accepted)

5. Conclusions

The omnichannel strategy involves a synergistic interaction. To create a unified brand experience, channel integration quality is an important way for customers to interact with customers during the purchasing process, regardless of the channel or stage they are in (Cummins, Peltier and Dixon, 2016).

According to our findings, “there is a relationship between brand omnichannel integration quality and brand omnichannel credibility” and thus supporting Süzer and Taşkın's (2021); Hossain et al.'s (2019); Huang, Lin and Cheng's (2019) findings. We found that “there is a relationship between brand omnichannel credibility and brand innovativeness” and thus supporting Jin et al. (2015); Martínez-de Albéniz & Belkaid (2020). Also, we found a relationship between brand omnichannel integration quality and brand innovativeness and this

supports Pappu & Quester (2016). Findings Show that *Brand omnichannel integration quality affect perceived omnichannel value*, and thus supporting Hamouda (2019); According to Krafft et al. (2015). Besides *in this study it is found that “Brand omnichannel credibility affect perceived omnichannel value”*, our results support Chen & Chi (2021); Gao and Yang (2016); Chaudhuri and Holbrook (2001). We state that brand innovativeness affects perceived omnichannel value and our results are supported with Schlager & Maas (2013). Our finding as “perceived omnichannel value affects omnichannel adoption” supports the studies of Eggert and Ulaga (2001) and Cheung et al. (2009).

Perceived value of consumers in their use of omnichannel did not have a mediating role in the effect of Perceived Integrated Channel Quality on Omnichannel Adoption. Perceived Omnichannel Value has been found to have a partial mediating role in the effect of Perceived Omnichannel Credibility on Omnichannel Adoption. Also, our results show that perceived brand innovativeness has a statistically significant effect on omnichannel adoption and perceived omnichannel value has a full mediator role in this effect.

The results about mediating effect of perceived omnichannel value between Perceived Omnichannel Credibility and Omnichannel Adoption; between perceived brand innovativeness and Omnichannel Adoption are supported with the theories of Davis (1989), Ajzen (1991) and models as “Information Adoption Model” (Figure 2) and “Wixom and Todd Model” (Figure 3). In addition, our conclusion about the perceived omnichannel value not having a mediating role in the effect of Perceived Integrated Channel Quality on Omnichannel Adoption could not be correlated with any other study since there was no study or theory examining this role. At this point, it is thought that this study contributes to the literature in every aspect.

This study contains many suggestions about omnichannel for marketing, brand, and supply chain managers in practice. With omnichannel applications, these managers can create a reliable channel for customers and create value by personalizing the distribution channel online and offline and making it accessible anywhere and anytime. This value is important for businesses to gain sustainable competitive advantage. At the same time, this value enables businesses to produce high quality goods and services by highlighting brand innovation. Also, it increases the trust of consumers within the omnichannel and reduces the risk in the shopping processes of consumers.

Businesses that provide omnichannel integration increase the perceived value of the consumer and provide them with a safer channel experience. Consumers who use a quality integrated system online and offline in the omnichannel distribution network can easily adapt to the channel and increase their satisfaction level. In fact, when it is considered that the brand loyalty of the consumers whose satisfaction level increases, omnichannel strategies gain functionality at this point. It will create a positive image for brands in the eyes of

consumers who can examine and buy the product and service they want to buy in an integrated system such as computers, phones, tablets, online applications, and physical stores.

Due to the increasing importance of omnichannel strategies in the market conditions and competitive environment, it can be said that the number of enterprises providing omnichannel digital technology services has increased with the digitalization process. This creates a new digital network that provides services for brands. For this reason, this study provides evidence that brands that cannot provide uninterrupted service to consumers online and offline in today's digital environment and fierce competition conditions will both be far from innovative perception and cannot create brand value. Businesses that implement Omnichannel strategies will be able to gain more competitive advantage among other businesses as they offer an integrated service in all distribution and communication channels.

This study is limited to tourism, banking, furniture, and clothing sectors. In future studies, the use of omnichannel can be investigated in sectors other than these sectors, or more detailed research can be conducted on these sectors. Future studies can identify different variables that affect the omnichannel and measure the perception of more quality and reliability. Since this study was conducted in Turkey, the scope of application of the study can be considered in different countries in terms of culture, personality, and demographic factors.

7. Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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